

Implant-Prosthodontic Rehabilitation with Short Implants: A Case Report with 1-Year Follow-up

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ABSTRACT/SUMMARY

Alveolar ridge atrophy represents a critical determinant in the planning and execution of implant-prosthodontic interventions. In this particular case, a contemporary, minimally invasive approach involving the utilization of short implants was adopted. A 68-year-old female patient, afflicted by a markedly atrophic edentulous mandible and concurrent hypertrophy of the attached gingiva in the anterior region, sought comprehensive implant-prosthodontic rehabilitation. The therapeutic course commenced with a vestibuloplasty procedure with secondary epithelialization, incorporating the application of Plasma Rich in Growth Factors (PRGF). Subsequently, the second surgical phase was carried out, precisely three weeks following the vestibuloplasty. Taking into account the profound bone resorption and the limited 2-3 mm of bone clearance above the alveolar nerve in the distal aspects of the mandible, four short implants measuring 4.0 x 5.0 mm in dimensions were positioned within the interforaminal region. Following the surgical procedure, multi-unit abutments and impression copings were promptly situated in order to take a monophasic polyether impression. The patient received a screw-retained fixed-prosthodontic provisional restoration composed of acrylic, spanning from the right lower first molar to the left lower first molar, within 48 hours after the surgical intervention. Four months later, the definitive screw-retained implant-supported fixed prosthesis was securely placed. The healing process proceeded without any complications, and one year after the loading, both clinical and radiographic assessments

reveal a stable outcome. In addition, the patient has expressed unequivocal contentment with the achieved results.

KEYWORDS: alveolar ridge atrophy; immediate loading; short implants; vestibuloplasty

INTRODUCTION

The rehabilitation of edentulous patients with alveolar atrophy poses a significant challenge for healthcare practitioners operating within the domains of oral surgery and prosthodontics. Edentulism, often caused by various pathogenic factors such as dental caries, periodontal diseases, traumatic injuries, and oral malignancies results in the manifestation of residual ridge resorption [1]. The volumetric content of the residual ridge exhibits a progressive reduction following a series of morphological alterations, a phenomenon that has been scientifically depicted as "residual ridge reduction" [2]. Particularly, the most substantial reduction in residual ridge size occurs within the initial six months, persisting at a diminished pace throughout an individual's lifetime [1]. This resorptive phenomenon has been characterized as a persistent, gradual, irreversible, and catabolic progression. Elderly women and estrogen insufficiency have demonstrated a tendency towards narrower ridges, and vitamin supplementation helped with mitigating ridge resorption [1]. Consequently, this ongoing resorptive process may culminate in insufficient bone volume, a prerequisite for the effective placement and enduring viability of dental implants. In addressing the need to enlarge vestibular depth, practitioners may employ various vestibuloplasty techniques, selecting the most suitable approach in accordance with the remaining bone height [3]. The incorporation of platelet concentrates, such as Platelet-Rich Growth Factor (PRGF), may also be considered as part of the procedure [4]. In scenarios characterized by alveolar atrophy and anatomical constraints, there is a great clinical interest in the utilization of short implants as prosthodontic carriers. Short implants are defined as those with a length of 8 mm or less, primarily designated for deployment in posterior edentulous regions featuring atrophic alveolar ridges, provided that the width of the alveolar ridge permits their placement [5]. It is noteworthy that length of the implant may not necessarily exert a beneficial influence on the stress distribution on the implant [6]. Enlarging the implant's diameter tends to mitigate the stress intensity distributed along its length [6]. The objective of this case report is to present a case involving an extensively atrophied mandible and to delineate its implant-prosthodontic rehabilitation.

CASE REPORT

A 68-year-old female patient presented herself at the Department of Oral Surgery, University Hospital Centre Zagreb, seeking resolution for an extensively atrophic edentulous mandible. Following a comprehensive health history assessment, it was determined that there were no contraindications for implant-prosthodontic therapy. The patient's medical history revealed the absence of any documented medical conditions or medication intake. The patient reported experiencing neuralgic pain attributed to the pressure exerted by the buccal wings of her complete denture. Subsequent clinical examination revealed soft tissue hypertrophy resulting from irritation caused by an inappropriate lower complete denture, along with hypersensitivity and pain in the areas corresponding to both mental nerves. Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) confirmed alveolar bone resorption as well as partial basal bone resorption. The width of the frontal mandibular region was deemed

adequate. However, the ridge exhibited pronounced sharpness and required leveling. In the distal regions, specifically 36 and 46, the ridge width measured approximately 2.5 millimeters (mm), which fell short of being sufficient for implantation, even when considering the use of short implants. Nevertheless, the alveolar ridge dimensions in interforaminal region allowed the placement of four short implants, each measuring 4.0 mm in diameter and 5.0 mm in length.

The initial surgical procedure encompassed vestibuloplasty with secondary epithelialization, involving the application of Plasma Rich in Growth Factors (PRGF). During this operation, the hypertrophic mobile mucosa was excised, and the flap edges were repositioned at the base of the vestibular fornix. Pre-prepared PRGF clots were taken and sutured using a resorptive suture 5/0. The wound was left to heal *per secundam*. Three weeks later, a second procedure was conducted, involving the placement of four short BTI implants (Biotechnology Institute SL, Vitoria, Spain), each with a diameter of 4.0 mm and a length of 5.0 mm, in regions 33, 35, 43, and 45 (Figure 1). The implantation procedure commenced at a rotation speed of 800 rpm with a torque of 35 Ncm, followed by a transition to a biological drilling technique at a speed of 65 rpm without irrigation to prevent bone necrosis and facilitate the creation of an entirely biological implant bed (Figure 1). Subsequent to implantation, Implant Stability Quotient (ISQ) measurements were obtained using the Penguin RFA system (Integration Diagnostics Sweden AB, Gothenburg, Sweden), revealing a high primary stability value of 75 ISQ. Following the surgical component of therapy, a panoramic radiograph was taken for evaluation (Figure 2). Afterwards, transfer components were positioned, and a monophasic impression was taken by using a polyether impression material (ImpregumPenta, 3M ESPE, Seefeld, Germany) to manufacture a screw-retained fixed-prosthetic provisional restoration composed of Polymethyl Methacrylate (PMMA). This provisional restoration was placed within 48 hours after implantation (immediate loading). Four months later, the final screw-retained implant-supported fixed prosthesis was affixed (Figure 3). A year after prosthodontic loading, no clinical or radiographic changes concerning the implants were observed. Peri-implant marginal bone levels remained stable, and the patient expressed complete satisfaction with the overall results.

Figure 1: a: Preparation of the implant bed by biological drilling technique. b: Implantation of the short implant. c: Suturing of the area after the implantation.

Figure 2: Control pan or a micradio graph taken on the day of implantation.

Figure 3: a-b: Final screw-retained implant-supported fixed prosthesis placement.

DISCUSSION

The morphology of the alveolar bone is an essential factor in the context of rehabilitating edentulous patients [7]. Investigations about morphological alterations in the facial skeleton of edentulous individuals have revealed that the reduction in height within the anterior aspect of the maxillary process is significantly smaller, approximately fourfold, compared to the change in height observed in the alveolar process of the mandible [7]. This discrepancy can be attributed to several factors, including the broader surface area, thinner cortical bone, and denser trabecular bone structure of the maxilla, which facilitate a more efficient transmission and dispersion of forces. In lower jaw, resorption of the residual alveolar ridges manifests as a forward-upward rotation, accompanied by a reduction in the occlusal vertical dimension [7].

Vestibuloplasty represents a surgical intervention characterized by the manipulation of soft tissue attachments within the oral vestibule. Its primary objective is to enlarge a denture-bearing area and to elevate the residual alveolar ridge height [8]. Vestibuloplasty with secondary epithelization is specifically indicated when the residual bone height is deemed satisfactory, yet the oral vestibule exhibits deficiencies attributable to mucosal inadequacy or suboptimal quality. In our particular case, PRGF clots were applied and secured to the mandibular alveolar ridge periosteum using resorbable sutures. This method stimulates epithelialization, promotes the formation of attached mucosal tissue, and enlarges vestibular depth through the action of growth factors. Mozzati M, et al. [9] conducted research employing a PRGF to overcome the limitations associated with conventional surgical interventions. In their study, the PRGF test group reported no postoperative complications, while the control group exhibited two cases of postoperative swelling and mild bleeding [9].

Kothari CR, et al. [10] employed amnion as a graft material to expand the vestibulum and facilitate the formation of newly attached mucosal tissue. They monitored the vestibular healing process at one, two and four weeks, and three months postoperatively, achieving a notable vestibular enlargement which indicated that amnion serves as a suitable graft material for vestibuloplasty [10]. Collectively, the cited literature supports our assertion that the novel approach of vestibuloplasty with secondary epithelialization holds promise for the expansion of attached mucosal areas and the acquisition of a substantial quantity of healthy mucosal tissue surrounding future implant sites. Historically, the adoption of shorter implants was discouraged due to higher failure rates. Consequently, emphasis was placed on maximizing implant length to enhance the prospects of implant success. However, a contemporary paradigm shift has emerged, favoring shorter implants under the "stress-minimizing surgery" paradigm [11]. This transition is underpinned by several advantages, including reduced clinical complexity, shorter surgical durations, diminished treatment costs, and improved patient-reported outcomes. Recent clinical investigations, when comparing the results of short and longer implants placed in the posterior regions of the jaws, have unveiled that reduced-length implants could be deemed a promising therapeutic option for addressing ridge deficiencies during rehabilitation [11].

The implant diameter is also a critical factor in stress distribution, with the crestal bone area receiving the highest stress, while minimal stress is transferred apically [12]. Increasing implant length primarily contributes to the enhancement of initial stability, while an increase in implant width serves a dual purpose by fortifying initial stability and concurrently enlarging the functional surface area at the crestal bone level [12]. This broader functional surface area facilitates superior distribution of occlusal forces. Substantiating this concept, finite element analysis has provided empirical support, revealing that implant length may not serve as the principal determinant governing the transmission of occlusal loads to the bone-implant interface [12].

Furthermore, the success of short implants must be considered from a prosthodontic rehabilitation perspective. Wu H, et al. [13] conducted a meta-analysis to assess the risk of short implant failure with immediate loading, revealing that immediately loaded short implants do not exhibit a higher risk of implant-prosthodontic therapy failure when compared to standard implants. The results of recent review article by Rameh S, et al. [11] have demonstrated that when short implants are appropriately utilized, they yield viable and promising results even after five years of functional use. This is conditioned with their placement in accordance with a comprehensive surgical and prosthodontic protocol that takes into account various biomechanical factors crucial for optimizing long-term prognosis [11]. It is advisable to conduct future studies with extended observation periods to validate and establish the long-term predictability of these outcomes [14].

CONCLUSION

Considerable atrophy of the edentulous mandible, coupled with soft tissue hypertrophy, presents a plausible opportunity for intervention through vestibuloplasty techniques with secondary epithelialization, incorporating the application of Plasma Rich In Growth Factors (PRGF). Following this procedure, implant-prosthodontic therapy can be applied, utilizing short implants as the carriers for prosthodontic restorations. This approach has yielded noteworthy outcomes, including a marked expansion of the vestibulum gingivae propriae, enhanced epithelialization, diminished postoperative discomfort, and reduced edema. Furthermore, following the placement of short implants in biologically-prepared implant beds, no postoperative complications were documented, ensuring the successful execution of implant-prosthodontic therapy.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

All authors declare no conflicts of interest.

ETHICS

The ethics committee approved implementation of the present study, the reference number: 05-PA-30-15-2/2023

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AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization, AC, DG; methodology, MZC, TK, DG; investigation, TK and VP; writing-original draft preparation, MZC, VP, writing-review and editing, AC, TK and SM. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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